

Comparison of German, British, and French colonial education policies in Cameroon and impacts

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Abstract: This paper focuses on Colonial education policies that were launched by the colonial powers in the colonial era in Cameroon. Using a historical methodology and a critical analysis of various empirical material and empirical literature, this paper investigates the different orientations that were given to Western education in Cameroon by the German, the British, and the French administrations in their respective colonial administration periods. It also compared them to expose their differences and common points. The investigation showed that the colonial education that was imposed on Cameroonians by these three countries was a poor content educational system for basic skills development, oriented toward a Christianization for domination or assimilation, and exploitation purposes. The colonial education has not only deeply affected the local culture and epistemology but succeeded in attaching local people to the Eurocentric paradigm to the detriment of their values and culture. As a consequence, there has been an abandonment of local paradigms and educational principles, and also divisions regarding the different colonial master's heritage difference which has participated in the ongoing Cameroon secessionist crisis. In terms of governance, the French system was more direct, compared to the British and the German colonial administrations which charged the Christian Missionaries to conduct the education mission; but overall, the objective and the curriculum content were the same: introducing a western-style education that can help the exploitation of the colony.

Keywords: German Kamerun; French Cameroon; British Cameroon; colonial education; religious mission; exploitation,

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Introduction

Cameroon is one of the rare countries in Africa that has experienced three different colonial rules. The German administration was the first European colonial power to impose its domination on "Kamerun" (Cameroon) from 1884 (Ngho, 1988; Owona, 1996, p. 28); the end of their rule was precipitated by their defeat Cameroon is one of the rare countries in Africa that has experienced three different colonial rules. The German administration was the first European colonial power to impose its domination on "Kamerun" (Cameroon) from 1884 (Ngho, 1988; Owona, 1996, p.

28); the end of their rule was precipitated by their defeat in the First World War by countries amongst which the United Kingdom (Hereafter UK) and France, who participated in seizing the German colonies in Africa. That is how the German colonizers were replaced in Cameroon by France and the United Kingdom, for much longer colonial rules upon Cameroon even if it was initially said to be provisional. The territory was divided between these two countries in March 1916 as League of Nations mandates (Joseph, 1986, p. 43). Between 1916 and 1922, the territory was administered by Britain and France as part of their African colonial possessions. However, in 1922, the League of Nations was established to ensure world peace and prevent future wars. The peoples of Cameroon would be placed under the mandate of the League of Nations, according to Article 22 paragraph 5. Despite Britain and France's acceptance of the League of Nations' General Provisions, it was clear that France intended to administer the territory as an integral part of the French overseas empire (Ndille, 2018; Owona, 1996). Britain and France declared their intentions to be responsible for "... the promotion of the material and moral well-being and social progress of their inhabitants" as part of the point 12 Mandate Agreement that followed in 1922 (Ndille, 2018; Owona, 1996).

After a serious decolonization war conducted by the Cameroonian liberation movement called Union of the Peoples of Cameroon (UPC), the colonial masters were prepared to leave. The French colonial administrators ruled their part of the country until 1960, while the British masters' ruling ended a year after, in 1961 (Deltombe et al., 2011; Joseph, 1986; Ngoh, 1979; Tchouankap, 2010, p. xii). As colonial powers in Cameroon, Germany, UK and France initiated several actions among which the introduction of a Western education system; they fought and put away the traditional educational system and imposed Western (European) forms of education that shaped Cameroon, and influenced its trajectory up to the present day.

The present Cameroonian conflict which broke out in 2016, and has already made more than 4,000 civilian deaths in the North-West and South-West regions (Watch, 2022), constitutes an undisputable identity crisis according to the claims of the minority English speaking part of the country (about 20%). It is the protestation of this minority of Cameroonians colonized by the UK, against the majority part of the country (about 80%) which inherited the French colonial education, culture, and way of doing, for attempting to erase their British colonial heritage that launched the crisis in 2016 (Cameroon radio and Television Crtv, 2020; Ndille, 2021). The importance of revisiting the educational background of Cameroon which continues to affect the country's destiny to date appears to be of higher importance in understanding and solving several problems that constitute obstacles to Cameroon's progress development. It is paramount to the policymakers' work as historians often affirm that it is necessary to take a few steps behind to leap well. This research investigates the different orientations that were given to Western education in Cameroon by the German, the British, and the French administrations in their respective colonial administration periods. It also compared them to expose their differences and common points before ending on their consequences in the First World War by countries amongst which the United Kingdom (Hereafter UK) and France, who participated in seizing the German colonies in Africa. That is how the German colonizers were replaced in Cameroon by France and the United Kingdom, for much longer colonial rules upon Cameroon even if it was initially said to be provisional. The territory was divided between these two countries in March 1916 as League of Nations mandates (Joseph, 1986, p. 43). Between 1916 and 1922, the territory was administered by Britain and France as part of their African colonial possessions. However, in 1922, the League of Nations was established to ensure world peace and prevent future wars. The peoples of Cameroon would be placed under the mandate of the League of Nations, according to Article 22 paragraph 5. Despite Britain and France's acceptance of the League of Nations' General Provisions, it was clear that France intended to administer the territory as an integral part of the French overseas empire (Ndille, 2018; Owona, 1996). Britain and France declared their intentions to be responsible for "... the promotion of the material and moral well-being and social progress of their inhabitants" as part of the point 12 Mandate Agreement that followed in 1922 (Ndille, 2018; Owona, 1996).

After a serious decolonization war conducted by the Cameroonian liberation movement called Union of the Peoples of Cameroon (UPC), the colonial masters had to leave; the French masters ruled their part of the country until 1960, while

the British masters' ruling ended a year later, in 1961 (Deltombe et al., 2011; Joseph, 1986; Ngoh, 1979; Tchouankap, 2010, p. xii). As colonial powers in Cameroon, Germany, UK and France initiated several actions among which the introduction of a Western education system; they fought and put away the traditional educational system and imposed Western (European) forms of an education system that shaped Cameroon, and influenced its trajectory up to the present day.

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Research Methodology

This paper used document analysis as a qualitative research method to investigate the motivations, the content, and the consequences of the different educational systems introduced during the colonial era in Cameroon. In qualitative research, data analysis allows researchers to delve into and understand the behaviors, experiences, and meanings that people associate with the phenomenon being studied (Creswell, 2009). Several scholars (Cohen et al., 2017; Creswell, 2012; Herrera & Merceron, 2013; Snape & Spencer, 2003) have identified interviews, observations, documents, and audiovisuals as data sources in qualitative research. Documents are a type of data that a researcher can use to back up his or her research. Electronic or printed documents are both acceptable (Bowen, 2009). The pieces of information provided in documents are usually not created by the researcher, but rather result from the collection and compilation of images and texts that document issues, experiences, and regulations, activities among other things (Bowen, 2009; Ingleby, 2012). Documents can be primary or secondary. Primary documents include field notes from participant observations, interview transcripts, and photographs, to name a few, while secondary documents include demographic data, records, surveys, database information, and much more (Schensul et al. 1999). According to O'Leary (2014), documents come in three varieties: public records, personal documents, and physical evidence. Personal documents include emails, blogs, individual websites, journals, and so on; public records include reports, handbooks, institutional/company websites, syllabi, and so on; and physical evidence includes photographs, artifacts, posters, and so on (Bowen, 2009; Taylor et al., 2016). In this paper, public records, syllabi, and literature are used. An important part of the literature used for this research includes books and articles on colonization in Cameroon, colonial education in Cameroon, explorers, merchants, and Missionaries' activities in the country. We also use official texts and regulations launched by the colonial administrations to organize their respective colonized spheres.

Document analysis is considered a systematic examination and interpretation of documents to gain insight and knowledge (Bowen, 2009; Taylor et al., 2016). Analyzing documents entails coding data to create themes from which realistic conclusions or meanings can be drawn. From Bowen's (2009) perspective, document analysis is frequently used to corroborate findings from other data sources, such as interviews, in a process known as triangulation. In this research, we examine the themes that emerge from the literature, as well as the documents, following the document analysis method.

Different colonial powers and their educational policies in Cameroon

In this part, the different colonial administrations’ educational policies are going to be presented. The German first, then the French, and the British thirdly.

A- In the German Era (1884 to 1916)

When German arrived in Cameroon in 1884, they were not initially interested in establishing an educational system (Omatseye & Omatseye, 2008). Their targets were to protect their interests in Cameroon, realize some projects, occupy the territory, and exploit the colony as much as possible. After a certain moment, they found out that they could extract more from the colony if they could use more local people after teaching them the German language and some basic skills; that is how they found the imposition of a colonial educational system a good investment (Omatseye & Omatseye, 2008), which could help them to extract more and faster the resources of the colony.

The first schools they created were private. The German Alfred Woerman, shop owner gave the start by opening a primary school in 1885. In 1886, he submitted a project to the German administration not only to open a primary school, but also a school to train artisans, and another one to train agricultural monitors (Engelbert Atangana, 2010). During the same year, a request from the Vatican to implement schools in Cameroon was addressed to the German government; and Otto Von Bismark’s Government authorized Catholic priests to open schools in Cameroon.

From 1887 to 1905, some private schools sprang up in Douala, Victoria, Garoua, and Yaounde. “The curriculum in the early year of primary school concentrated on Christian religious knowledge, and German language” (Omatseye & Omatseye, 2008, p. 24). In April 1910, the German administration enacted the Education Law which addressed the following:

- (i) Prescribing the German Language as the only medium of instruction in schools. However, the Douala language could also be used, therefore restricting the use of the mother tongue in schools;*
- (ii) Primary education had a duration of five years of which stipulated minimum knowledge was to be acquired;*
- (iii) Primary education was made compulsory for all children of school age;*
- (iv) Subventions were to be given to mission schools on the conditions that they encouraged and emphasized the use of the German language and the expression of the culture. They would also promote German colonial policy. To make this workable, Cameroonians were sent to Germany for further studies (Ngoh, 1988).*

Despite the enactment of this Law that showed the growing interest of the German administration to impose a Western educational system on Cameroonians, it did not get directly involved in school creation. In 1910, they were only two public schools in Cameroon: one in Douala, and another one in Victoria (which became Limbe) (Engelbert Atangana, 2010); while in 1913, the missionaries already owned 613 schools in Cameroon, mostly located in the southern part of the country (Ngonga, 2010, p. 19). As we can observe in Table 1, during the whole colonial German era in Cameroon, almost all the schools were owned by the missionaries.

Table 1: The educational system under the German Colonization

	Percentage of Students	Number of students
Public schools	2,39%	847
Missionaries Schools	97,70	35986

Source: (Ngonga, 2010, p. 19).

At that moment, the total population of the country was evaluated to about 2 230 000 people with 36 833 students. The public sector had only 2.3% of the students while the Christian religious missions had 97.7% of the students. About the curriculum, the program was 5 years for all the primary schools as stipulated in the education Law of April 1910. The content was a little bit different. The two public schools (Douala and Limbe) each had 4 classes taught by European teachers and assisted by Cameroonian teachers. The curriculum was made of five main content as shown in the following table:

Table 2: Curriculum of the public primary schools in 1910.

List of sub-jects	number of hours per day in the 1 st year	number of hours per day in the 2 nd year	number of hours per day in the 3 rd year	number of hours per day in the 4 th year	number of hours per day in the 5 th year
German	2	2	4	4	4
Lesson of things	2	3	3	3	3
Calculation	2	3	3	3	3
Geography	-	-	1	1	1
Natural history	-	-	-	1	1
Total	6	8	11	12	12

Source: (Engelbert Atangana, 2010)

This table shows that the curriculum included three (3) subjects in the first two years, three (3) in the third year, and five (5) in the two last years. The German language was one-third of the daily learning of the pupils; employment of locals required them to be able to speak, read and write some Deutsch. It is also observable that other subjects like calculation and lessons on things were also important.

Two main Christian religious missions were represented in the field: the Protestant Mission and the Catholic Mission. For the Protestant Mission which owned about 200 schools in 1912, the overall aim of the educational system was to *“free the youth from the pagan world and take them to God”* (Engelbert Atangana, 2010; Ewane, 1985, p. 80). Christianity was the most important tool used in the missionary schools to establish the domination of the colonial master through his white Western God over the *“darkness”* or *“blackness”* of the local people and their Gods. Too much time was spent on mastering the Christian religion and the German language, which shows that it was the main purpose of the education system introduced (Malisa & Missedja, 2019, p. 2). Following the nature of religions which are not usually submitted to discussions and critics when they are thought, students were then trained to believe, to memorize more than to think. It was more about conversion than education.

The content of the subject History taught comprised the history of Germany, the history of Spain, the history of Italia, and the history of Cameroon); in the part concerning the history of Cameroon, the focus was consistently geared toward the Christianization of Cameroon, on the actions of former German governors in Cameroon, and on what positive things the Europeans explorer did after they arrived in the country (Engelbert Atangana, 2010, p. 62). Concerning German History, the program was orientated toward the Christianization of Europe, and the history of Catholicism in Germany and Europe. The courses on Geography were more about the geography of European and the geography of Africa. Concerning mathematics, the missionaries had a critical racial bias toward Cameroonians; they strongly believed that Africans (black people) in general were not intelligent enough to understand mathematics. That is why they chose to

limit the course to very basic operations and to teach it for only 2 hours per week while history was taught for 3 hours (Engelbert Atangana, 2010, p. 62).

The catholic which was the second more important religious group in building schools¹ had almost the same views as the protestant mission concerning the objectives of their education and the curriculum they developed. They made a slight difference in putting German language teaching in the first two years of the primary schools and in giving their main teachers possibilities to be creative in their teaching methods.

B- Educational policies in French Cameroon (1916 - 1960)

After the defeat of Germany in the First World War, Cameroon was set between France and Great Britain. France took the biggest part, about 4/5 of the surface of the country after negotiations with Great Britain (Owona, 1996). This part had the advantage to include almost all of the railway networks and the port. The French administration believed that the partition of Cameroon was not likely to be changed in a near future. In relation to the engagement they took at the United Nations Trusteeship to administer Cameroonians considered as a barbarian to civilization, they adopted an exclusive use of a policy of assimilation. From that time, the French administration in Cameroon had one major goal in mind: "to make their assimilation policy work. The assimilation aimed at creating a native Cameroonian elite class by totally replacing the African culture, language, and civilization with that of the French (Ndille, 2018, p. 3; Omatseye & Omatseye, 2008, p. 24). They decided to go further than German in erasing the African identity. They launched the "moral conquest" to break the cultural link between people and their traditional authorities (Kings).

In pursuance of this goal, Carde the high commissioner of France to Cameroon issued in 1921 an official note imposing French as the only language to be taught or to be used to teach in Schools in Francophone Cameroon (Ngonga, 2010) as cited in Carde, J, 1921. This shows that France did not give the possibility to use a local language in school as the German did. The French administration even created some public schools just to teach the French language. It intended the civilization and the language of natives would become French in every way. To make sure that things would be done in that way, all the schools established in French Cameroon were fully under the direct control of France. To reach this target, they first had to erase the German heritage except for Christianity which is part of their common cultural European identity. They got so fast in erasing the German legacy that in 1924, all the schools in French Cameroon were already using only French (Ndille, 2018).

The French Administration followed the path of German colonization by using missionaries to open schools. In 1920, a decree formalized the partnership between the colonial administration and the religious missions (Dupraz, 2015, p. 32); this same administrative regulation also forbade Missionaries to create schools where the Islam religion was dominating (North Cameroon). Our analysis of this situation is that the nature of the Arab religion which considers itself as the best and only good religion as the Christian religion does, makes it a bit radical in opposition to the African beliefs systems which tolerate more the fact that other people can have their own religious views; this may have been analyzed by European colonizers as a major obstacle in the re-conversion of black Cameroonians Muslims into Christianity. The French colonial administration promoted directly an important system of public schools.

Compare to the German era, the French brought some major changes to the educational system. First, they changed the primary school duration. They added one year to the five years duration during the German era. They put the entry age to 6 years old. They implemented primary schools with two curriculums: the metropolitan curriculum and another one adapted to suit the local people. The main goal of these primary schools was the prepare children for secondary education. Under French rule, school expansion and enrollment were increased as indicated in table 3.

Table 3: Enrollment of Primary schools in French Cameroon

years	Number of schools	Enrollment
1947	137	18 600
1951	203	28 594
1956	583	79 363
1961	977	151 635

Source: (Ngoh, 1988; Omatseye & Omatseye, 2008, p. 26)

As a major change in the education policy, we can also mention that the French developed more public schools as compared to the German and the British administrations. It was a consequence of many debates that took place in France earlier than the beginning of the 20th century. From those debates, France adopted to make a clear separation between religious and non-religious schools. However, they still entrusted religious missions to school creation. Under French rule, private schools had to receive authorization from the colonial administration, which was responsible for inspecting them, and they had to respect several requirements to be eligible for a subsidy (Dupraz, 2015, p. 32).

Furthermore, France built a secondary school system. This secondary education was patterned along with the model in France. It was therefore normal for students to earn a Baccalaureate directly from France as if there were attending school in France. With its rich curriculum, the main part of these schools can still be found in Cameroon today.

Table 4: secondary schools enrollment in French Cameroon

years	Number of schools	Enrollment
1947	3	704
1951	3	908
1956	3	1479
1961	20	4742

: (Source Ngoh, 1988; Omatseye & Omatseye, 2008, p. 26)

The secondary school system growth was slow from 1947 to 1956; but, from the eve of the independence (1956), the number of schools and enrollment grew very fast. The reason is that the French needed some trained native people, who could work in the independent state.

C- Educational Policies in British Cameroon (1916 to 1961)

The British colonial administration as its French administration counterpart settled down in Cameroon in 1916 after the defeat of Germany in the First World War. The British part of Cameroon became part of the British colony of Nigeria, administrated by Lagos (Dupraz, 2015, p. 8). The educational policy was more about converting local people to Christianity. It was heavily influenced by the 1922 report entitled "Education in Africa", issued by the Phelps-Stoke foundation in 1911 to advance social and economic development in Africa and the Americas (Dupraz, 2015, p. 31). This

report advocated a closer partnership between Christian missions and colonial government. It also pointed out that, the school was not equally balanced in terms of quality. In fact, in the British Cameroon context, there was a type of school called “Sunday Schools”, which were non-registered and were providing only religious education; there was also the formal type of schools that were registered, inspected, and subsidized based on efficiency(Engelbert Atangana, 2010).

Table 5: Primary schools enrollment in British Cameroon

years	Number of schools	Enrollment
1947	229	25200
1951	266	28960
1956	385	46754
1961	499	86 257

Source: Owono.M, Colonial education in Cameroun; Jim, N, O., & Bridget, O, O., 2008, p27 (as cited in Nghoh, V. J. (1988).

An important fact to mention about education policy during the British rule is that they did not create any public schools. Instead, they transferred the resources to missionaries to expand education.

Before the Second World War, except for very few post-primary training schools for teachers and health personnel, there was essentially no secondary schools in Cameroon (Dupraz, 2015, p. 34). The British as the French administration also established a system of secondary schools; but, it was not large in terms of the number of schools, nor rich in terms of curriculum content as the one created in the French Cameroon colonial sphere.

Table 6: Enrollment of Secondary schools in British Cameroon

years	Number of schools	Enrollment
1947	1	704
1951	2	322
1956	3	468
1961	6	903

Source: Owono, Colonial education in Cameroun; Jim& Bridget, 2008, p27 (as cited in Nghoh, V. J. (1988).

From table 6, we can note that its growth was very slow. The reason is that most of the students in the British area who wanted to pursue their studies at the beginning of their rule were sent to secondary schools in Nigeria, mostly in the Umahia College located in the Owerri province.

Comparative analysis

The comparative analysis is going to be conducted first on the objectives and curriculum content of the colonial educational policies, and secondly on the governance and funding.

A- On the objectives and curriculum content

- Educating to facilitate the exploitation purpose

On the Objectives of their educational policies, it appears from the analysis that all of them, the German, the French, and the British colonial administration's policies in education were enacted to promote an educational system that can produce some human capacities that could be used in extracting faster and consistently the resources of the colony. In other words, their educational policies were orientated toward the facilitation of the Colony. In any case, however, the education policies they made reflected their desires. Their different colonial education programs all aimed at serving their interests, erasing local culture and fostering their culture, and promoting their economy in Europe. If they wanted clerks, they introduced a program to train clerks; when they needed assistant teachers, they introduced a program to produce them.

- Education for evangelization

Another important point to mention is the relationship between religion and education. British and German colonial administrations most of the time did not get directly involved in the school creation. The Germans creates only two public schools, while the British did not create any. While the French created a lot of public schools, but still entrusted Christian religious missions to establish some. They preferred having a strong partnership with Christian missions; that is how a very important part of the colonial activities in Cameroon was carried out by Christian Missions and some important missionaries such as Alfred Saker from the half of the 19th Century (Joseph, 1986, p. 48; Lange, 2000, p. 56). At their arrival, they started was considered by Richard Joseph as one of the most intense religious conversion activities in Central Africa to the point that in 1960, approximately 1 150 000 persons, representing the half of the Bulu community in South Cameroon was already converted (Joseph, 1986, p. 48). When we go back early in 1884 to the Berlin Conference, where all the European countries planned how they were going to colonize Africa, we observe that indirectly, the religious missions were involved in their strategy. The General Act of the Berlin Conference was issued on the 26th February 1885; in its first chapter, the Article 6 mentions:

“Provisions relating to the protection of the natives, of missionaries and travelers, and religious liberty

Article 6: *All the Powers exercising sovereign rights or influence in the aforesaid territories bind themselves to watch over the preservation of the native tribes {...}. They shall, without distinction of creed or nation, protect and favor all religious, scientific, or charitable institutions and undertakings created and organized for the above ends, or which aim at instructing the natives and bringing home to them the blessings of civilization.*

Christian missionaries, scientists, and explorers, with their followers, property, and collections, shall likewise be the objects of special protection. Freedom of conscience and religious toleration are expressly guaranteed to the natives, no less than to subjects and foreigners. The free and public exercise of all forms of divine worship, and the right to build edifices for religious purposes, and to organize religious missions belonging to all creeds, shall not be limited or fettered in any way whatsoever” (General Act of the Berlin Conference on West Africa , 26 February 1885).

Instead of creating schools directly, the colonial masters chose to transfer financial resources to missions. And this situation led to educational content that over-stressed converting people to Christianity. In pursuing their target of erasing the local culture and replacing it with their cultural order, they also stressed language studies.

During the colonization of Cameroon, all the colonial masters did not want to establish schools in the area where the Muslim religion was predominant. That was because they knew that it could be very difficult. After all, they wanted to impose the Christian religion on Cameroonians through education. It was also prohibited for Missions to create schools in such a context. Consequently, as figure 1 shows, the education policies have neglected the Muslim Area (North Cameroon).

Fig 1: Dissemination of schools and Numbers of students in Christian areas and Muslim areas (Source: built from OYONO.F, History of the Cameroonian Colonialism, 1985).

Since the South of the country was deeply converted into Christianity and the North the less converted, the South received most of the Missions and Missioners' efforts in the introduction of colonial education. It is estimated that in 1959, 71% of primary school-age children were enrolled in the South compared to 10 to 40% from the Center of the Country to the North. In some places in the North which were the most converted to the Islamic religion, this percentage of enrolled students reached 2% (Joseph, 1986, p. 48). This situation has created an unbalanced national educational development due to the evangelization mission behind the education provided. The Nord that was already attached to Islam refused to adopt the western type of schools because it was conditioned in a certain way by the acceptance of Christianity. That can be generalized to other African countries located near the equator such as Nigeria, Benin, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Togo, and Mali, and to explain why the Nord of these countries lag behind in terms of Western education model adoption and integration. They were reticent toward Western cultural education, and the Missionaries and colonial administrators were less interested in building schools for people that they cannot control at least mentally through their religious beliefs.

The colonial Educational from 1884 to 1960 at the independence of Cameroon was poor in the sense that it did not give important technical skills to local people. When it came to vocational or technical education, the local people were trained in a few subjects as very low-level technicians (agricultural monitors, assistant teachers, artisans); this is to ensure that in no way they could lean on the education received to compete with Europeans. As the policy was to keep local people "under-developed" and dominated, nowhere at no time was higher technical or vocational education promoted. Everything was done to keep Cameroon in the position of country supplier of raw materials and not in a position of an industrialized country.

- Creation of secondary education in French and English Camerouns

Overall, a difference in the types of schools and the curriculum can be noted between the education policies in colonial Cameroon between the German Era on the one hand and the British and the French eras on another; the education policies during the German era developed only primary schools and almost all the schools were missionary schools. While the French and the British administrations' educational policies created secondary schools.

Basic education was the priority for all these colonial administrations. Secondary schools were created late (in the British and French periods), in a context of organized, massive, and radical emancipation struggle mainly conducted by movements of liberation such as the Union of Peoples of Cameroon (hereafter UPC) in Cameroon. Created on April 10th, 1948, the UPC is considered as the spirit and the main body of the liberation movement in the country (Joseph, 1986). The decade 1940-1950 in which the first secondary schools were created constitutes the period in which the struggle of the several Workers Unions and the UPC started to become a serious threat to both the British and the French colonial administrations. Which led them to think about how they could "continue to stay" after leaving. The basic education

they were providing could not help people leading the Western type of State organization they wanted to leave local people with. They had to add secondary education to ensure that the first batches of local administrators would be trained in their system, and easily controlled, even after they leave the country.

B- On governance and funding

One of the most important differences found is about the administration of the schools. The British colonial education system was less centralized than the French. While the German and the British entrusted Christian missions, financing them through a system of grant-in-aid to develop education. As Ndille (2018) precised, instead of Britain bearing the financial burden as the administering authority, educational financing was carried out with funds derived from taxing indigenous peoples (Ndille, 2018, p. 5). Local education committees evolved into formal education authorities throughout the period. Local education committees were entrusted with the administration of primary education in their respective areas. The idea behind local education committees was to pique local interest and foster collaboration between local communities and the government. In this way, they could invest less for the same result. The French administration developed a strong network of public schools and mission schools that were centrally controlled from France (Gifford and Weiskel, 1971, p2 as cited in (Dupraz, 2015)). There is an important argument developed by some authors like Tchouankap (2010) defending that Britain was having more territories in different continents to administer compared to France and that they could not have enough human resources to maintain a tight administration system on the colonized territory in Cameroon. Observing that many British people settle down in South Africa, and left their colonial territories like Zambia, and Zimbabwe only late, 20 to 30 years after France left the French colonial territories in Africa shows that the British were also much attached to their African colonial spheres.

About the aim of the educational system, the French had an assimilation policy. They wanted to train a small administrative elite, while the British administration was more focused on converting as many as possible local people to Christianity.

Conclusion

The education policies in the colonial era in Cameroon have established an educational system used to serve the colonial masters' needs and interests. They implemented primary schools during the whole colonial period and secondary schools, especially during the French and British eras under the pressure of UPC's struggle for the liberation of the country from colonialism. The school network produced has been mostly established by religious missions. Concerning the curriculum content, there was an over-emphasis on the study of the colonial master's language, and the Christian religion (Engelbert Atangana, 2010). When it came to technical and vocational education, which could have helped in boosting the industrialization of the local economy, their education policies provided only basic knowledge on a few subjects to train low-level technicians. What the colonial master wanted the most was to train some people that they could use in the extraction of local resources. They also wanted to impose the Western paradigm and culture (western universalism) through religion, politics, and culture on the Cameroonian people. This education was not implemented for the development of local communities, but rather for the assimilation, the domination, and the exploitation of the natives' resources. It was therefore detrimental to local development. This educational system in any measure has been more disastrous to the local culture than useful.

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